

UNDERSTANDING OF RHINOLALIA SPEECH DEFECT AND MEASURES TO TREAT RHINOLALIA

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Annotation: rhinolalia is a common disease among the people, called by different names, indicating its negative effects on speech formation. This article provides information on rhinolalia and its types and measures for the treatment of rhinolalia.

Аннотация: ринолалия-распространенное в народе заболевание с разными названиями, проявляющее свое негативное влияние на формирование речи. В этой статье представлена информация о ринолалии и ее типах, а также о мерах лечения ринолалии.

Keywords: rhinolalia, hard palate, soft palate, sound, respiratory system, operation, speech therapy, medical treatment.

Ключевые слова: ринолалия, твердое небо, мягкое небо, звук, дыхательная система, операция, логопедическое обучение, лечение.

Rhinolalia is a speech disorder that causes problems in the pronunciation of sounds, especially nasal sounds. This disturbance is usually caused by whether or not the sound airflow passes through the nasal cavity. Rhinolalia is divided into two types:

Open rhinolalia (rhinophonia): in this case, the amount of air passing through the nose increases, which leads to an increase in nasal sounds (Nasalization) of speech sounds. Open rhinolalia can occur for the following reasons:

- Congenital anomalies of the hard or soft palate (for example, palate rupture).
- Paralysis or weakness of the muscles of the palate.
- Complications that occur after operations.

Features: all sounds or some sounds come out through the nose. When hearing speech, nasal sounds are clearly noticeable.

Closed rhinolalia: in this case, the amount of air passing through the nose decreases or disappears, which leads to a decrease in nasal sounds. Closed rhinolalia can occur for the following reasons:

- Slope of the nasal barrier (septum).
- The presence of nasal polyps.
- Enlargement of the adenoids (nasal glands).
- Allergic rhinitis or nasal inflammation.

Features: nasal sounds are mispronounced or lost. Speech seems to come out through the nose.

Treatment of rhinolalia varies depending on its cause. This may include surgical interventions, speech therapy exercises, or medication. It is recommended to consult a specialist and draw up a treatment plan.

Diagnosis of rhinolalia

Medical examination: examination of the oral and nasal cavity, soft palate.

Sound analysis: an assessment of the acoustic properties of sound and speech by a speech therapist.

Instrumental methods: Nasopharyngoscopy, videofluoroscopy, resonance imaging.

MEASURES FOR THE TREATMENT OF RHINOLALIA

Medical Treatments:

Surgical procedures: surgical intervention may be required to correct nasopharyngeal palate insufficiency or cracks.

Treatment of nasal pathologies: surgical intervention or drug therapy to eliminate nasal polyps, adenoids or curvature of the nasal wall.

Speech Therapy Training:

Exercises with speech: exercises are held that teach correct breathing and correct formation of sounds. Speech teaches how to control the air coming out through the nose and pronounce sounds correctly.

Breathing exercises:

Breathing control: special breathing exercises to train proper breathing through the nose. These exercises improve the ability to

control the air that comes out through the nasal and oral cavity when making sound.

Resonance therapy:

Vibration and resonance control: through special exercises, it is possible to teach to control the resonance of sounds, by which the sounds that come out through the nose can be reduced.

Support tools:

Prostheses and apparatus: in some cases, special prostheses or apparatus can be used to improve speech.

Psychological support:

Psychotherapy: psychotherapy helps to relieve stress and discomfort associated with speech defects. This will help the individual increase self-confidence and overcome difficulties with speech.

The methods of treatment of rhinolalia are individual and are selected depending on the condition of each patient. A team of experts, including otorhinolaryngologists, speech therapists and psychologists, collaborate in the development and implementation of the treatment plan.

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